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Актуализация проблемы отчуждения в современной литературе связана с необходимостью понимания его сущности и механизма в рамках единой концепции экзистенциализма в философской мысли. Отчуждение человека во многом связано с драматическими и трагическими факторами конкретного исторического процесса. В Азербайджанских романах 2000-х годов мотив отчуждения становится актуальным по разным причинам: на передний план привносится сегодняшняя неопределенность на фоне контрастов детства и взрослой жизни, поиск цели и смысла жизни, взаимоотношения личности и общества. Также героям приходится выбирать альтернативу на фоне меняющихся структур и историко-политических событий вместе с предшествующими им поколениями, их тянет в свой мир. Даже если это и не отражено в произведениях, условия войны влияют на мысли и эмоции героев как фоновое настроение и управляют ими.

Abstract: The actualization of the problem of alienation in modern literature is connected with the necessity of understanding its essence and mechanism within the framework of a single concept of existentialism in philosophical thought. Alienation of a person is largely connected with dramatic and tragic factors of a specific historical process. In Azerbaijani novels of the 2000s, the motif of alienation becomes relevant for various reasons: today's uncertainty against the background of contrasts of childhood and adulthood, the search for the purpose and meaning of life, the relationship between the individual and society are brought to the forefront. Also, the heroes have to choose an alternative against the background of changing structures and historical and political events together with the generations preceding them, they are drawn to their world. Even if this is not reflected in the works, the conditions of the war influence the thoughts and emotions of the heroes as a background mood and control them.

Ключевые слова: отчуждение, роман, современная литература, экзистенциализм, общество, одиночество.

Key words: alienation, novel, contemporary literature, existentialism, society, loneliness

Introduction

Contemporary Azerbaijani prose summarizes the aesthetic searches of the century by reflecting the characteristic features of the art of the time and defines the perspectives of the culture of the future with its artistic experience and stylistic innovations. The end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century can be considered a new stage in Azerbaijani literature in terms of topics and issues. All the complexity and contradictions of the period formed by the objective socio-historical conditions had a decisive effect on the moral requirements of literature. "... renewal is an eternal process, and from this point of view, it is legitimate to expect a certain renewal process at least every twenty or thirty years in the history of the literature of any nation." [10, p.45]. The theme of alienation in contemporary Azerbaijani literature has become more relevant especially since the 90s of the last century. In the creative texts of the new century, attention to the problem began to be drawn to one degree or another in almost every novel.

The actualization of the problem of alienation in contemporary literature is related to the need to understand its essence and mechanism within the framework of the single concept of existentialism in philosophical thought. The alienation of man is mostly associated with the dramatic and tragic factors of a specific historical process. As scientific and technical progress develops, a gap is created between society and the natural environment, human spiritual development is defeated by the technological power of the world, and cultural values weaken.

The political and economic processes taking place in the world, the resulting cataclysms, and the igniting of the technical revolution determine the alienation of a person against the background of the global flow. A person who cannot even be the owner of his own destiny leaves the struggle because he realizes that he is controlled by an unknown mechanism: he is faced with the choice of either joining the flow and living like everyone else, or supporting that controlling mechanism and living well, or withdrawing into himself and showing passive protest by being alienated

from this order. The young man of the 2000s is a person who deeply feels the crises in the political and economic spheres in his personal life, brought up by the radical changes and concerns that are taking place not only in his country, but all over the world.

Main part

Gan Turali's novel "Mustafa" (2011) expresses the pain of the youth of the age in the image of the main hero, reflects his desire for existential freedom and his total alienation as a result of his efforts. The novel, which was created against the background of more journalistic incitement and philosophical thoughts, successfully expresses the spiritual experiences of people in the conditions of globalization. In the chain of cause and effect, we observe that the weakest link is the spiritual weakening of modern man.

Mustafa is a young man whose memory goes through zigzags. The despair created by the social chaos is also reflected in his personal life. Books are the only companion of a young man who is completely disgusted with the world. With this tool, his ideas fall into an idealistic direction, after a while he joins politics in the hope of making radical changes in society, but this time he is arrested and falls into despair again. Mustafa, who works as a teacher in the village, becomes even more lonely after three years of imprisonment. For Mustafa, books become an alternative world. The idealistic thinking presented by what they read contrasts with the terrible realities of life. Completely alienated from society and withdrawn, Mustafa often looks back and believes that something better is left in the past. In the novel, thanks to flashbacks and transitions to his story "Moonlight", which he wrote a few years ago, the hero's hopeless thoughts about the world, people and relationships are revealed. Mustafa has a pathological desire to distance himself from people; it seems to him that the multitude is an obstacle to his uniqueness.

Gan Turali's novel "Mustafa", which originates from Eastern and Western philosophical ideas, expresses the idea that "struggle is absolute, defeat is inevitable." Unfortunately, philosophical ideas and reasoning are realized in the novel more at the level of citation than becoming a fact of literature; the hero is a young man who memorizes what he has read and justifies his ideas as he comes to his place, in other words, his conclusions are formed more from books than from life. However, towards the end of the novel, the teacher who taught life to his student expresses what he learned from his own experience: "*Look, Akram, you are going to that city. I trained you not to become the next victim of that evil society. You will not be me. I know that. I have understood the reasons for my mistakes. I have explained those mistakes to you one by one. But I know you will make mistakes too. Life is not mathematics that you learn from notebooks and books. Life is both a book and a laboratory.*" [4, p.135].

Despite the dramatization of the situations, the novel is more an imitation of pain than a reflection of the grief of a young man. Mustafa is not a hero who has good reasons to run away from people and take refuge in solitude, a tormentor that suffered a lot, and who is ready to die for his ideals. "*There is no doubt that Gan*

Turali tries to symbolize the social consciousness of Azerbaijani youth with the image of Mustafa; but he can "read" this society only to the extent that it is visible (deconstructive). In the last chapter, the novelist tries to look at his hero from the outside; this chapter is written by someone else, Deniz: after imprisonment, Mustafa "returns" to the province, to a quiet teaching life; as if with this: as observed throughout the novel, the stuckness of the public consciousness in the book (enlightenment) stage is reaffirmed..." [2, p.35].

In Gan Turali's novel "Whip of fortune" (2016), self-awareness is already realized in parallel lines towards society and the inner world. In the work, the modern writer Mehdi's war is with the society that does not give him the value he deserves. In fact, this is not a struggle at all, but resentment, turning away. If the hero in the novel "Mustafa" declares that he fulfills his sacred duty, his main duty to humanity by writing the story "Moon light", Mehdi renounces it and withdraws into solitude due to the fact that the literature, which has completely lost its sanctity in the modern society where spirituality is eroded, turns against its essence. Mehdi does not choose the path of struggle either, he accepts its meaninglessness from the beginning, plunges into the whirlpool of drunken thoughts and begins to live a bohemian life. This moment of alienation described in the novel sums up the image of artists who withdraw and give up creativity because they cannot take the place they dream of in society. Nothing in his life can catch him, his thoughts are completely rooted in despair: "*Writing is an attempt to understand. How else can you explain the fact that writers live such a crazy life and are frivolous? They simply write down their attempts to understand life. Do you not see that many of them cannot speak about what they write? Because they are naive, pure. A person who understands life will not write a single word.*" [5, p.158]. Since Mehdi began to see art not through the mirror of aesthetics, but through the window of reality, and to evaluate the situation from this perspective, the idea of the unnecessaryness of literature alienates him from writing and the literary environment. Although this decision seems inevitable in the background of the hero's gains and losses in the novel, which creates a real picture of today with all its details, after a while he starts writing for the sake of Zeynab, who loves him.

Mehdi, the hero he created in his novel called "Whip of fortune", saves himself with art. In other words, the conclusions reached by Mehdi, the hero of Gan Turali, as a result of despair and disbelief, are realized in a completely different way in his work. The Sufi Mehdi created by Mehdi experiences the moment of alienation on the religious level: Sheikh Mehdi, who destroys the temple he worshiped and lived in for years, overcomes religious stereotypes and frees himself. Throughout the novel, his alienation from religious thought and religious people is reflected as a painful process. The Sufi Mehdi is looking for answers to his questions based on the dream of a woman. It is not at all easy to get away from the truths that he has believed and found for almost his whole life, and to completely change his path. Every question that he asked himself when he was alone, and he looked for answers in books,

in the words of his friend Abbas, and in his own heart, took him away from religion and the path of Sufism and brought him closer to a free and different way of thinking. As a result of alienation from religious thinking and sect, Sufi Mehdi finds his higher self, his "freedom". The reason for the clarification in his mind and the clarification of his thoughts is precisely the literature and the art of words that the writer Mehdi avoided. It is interesting that the writer Mehdi, who does not see art as a salvation in his life, writes the novel about him reaching the truth through art and struggling for this success. So, in fact, despite all his rebellion, Mehdi believes in the possibility of struggle in his ideal thought. He fulfilled Zeynab's persistent request and published the novel he had written, and on the day of the presentation, he committed suicide in front of the readers. Mehdi's last words confirm for the last time that he is, in fact, a hero alienated not from literature, but from a false literary environment: *"I betrayed myself by writing. This presentation, this suicide, is the punishment for my sin. God will surely forgive me..."* [5, p.219].

The novel "Leyli and Majnun" (2023), which highlights the main character's alienation from society against the backdrop of love, is a deconstructive work by Vahid Mammadli. Although written on the basis of classic plots, the protagonist of the novel, which gives a new essence to the idea and content, Gheys (Majnun), just like in classic texts, gains the "status" of obsession because of his love and affection. The reason that alienates him from the society and even his own family is the love that Gheys clings to in other thoughts "like crazy" and keeps alive in his existence. In the novel "Leyli and Majnun", which is based on the concept of Sufism, the main characters choose to reunite at the cost of condemnation by leaving their family and society as a whole in the path of love. What distinguishes this novel from the classic works "Leyli and Majnun" is the struggle of the lovers, their turning their backs on the society from which they were completely alienated on the way to meet each other. Although the reason for estrangement here seems to be only love at first glance, in fact, "breaking the cage" in the brain is only possible due to spiritual strength and free thinking. *"Vahid Mammadli's novel does not deny the classical idea, but it somehow overtakes it. The return of Majnun to Leyli is a return to himself, to his harmony, to himself."* [12, p.21]. Therefore, the idea of the novel "Leyli and Majnun" is more of an idea of freedom. Nevertheless, at the end of the play, the lovers can meet each other only as stars: *"The eyes of the lovers, embracing each other with longing, shone with a white light that dazzled both of them. The flood of light stretching across the sky gradually made the lovers invisible, and they themselves became light. After a while, this ball of light disappeared in the white light from the heavens, and the flood of light was drawn to the place from which it came. Dervishes (pious wanderers) watching this scene raised their hands and sang praises to you: - Thank you, great God. Your angels met and went to heaven..."* [9, p.156]. Thus, in the novel written by using elements of magical realism and postmodernism, the author emphasizes the inevitability of reality, the possibility of

turning one's back on society in this way only as a dream.. *"Freedom is never depicted as a possible outcome in the works of existentialist writers. Freedom is a horizon line that recedes as it approaches... The heroes of existentialist works cannot necessarily reach freedom; freedom is the way to freedom for them."* [6, p.59]. Majnun's freedom includes not only his personal self, but also Leyli's existence. So here Leyli is "another me", or the half of "me" that needs to be completed. If we take into account that the novel is based on the unity-body concept, where Leyli is God's light, particle, and therefore HIMSELF, the whole universe - Majnun treats Leyli as his essence, takes refuge in her as a way to God, as his home in the real world. In this regard, Leyli is the only exception who does not fall into the so-called "others" who are sympathetic, because she is not an other, but a complement, a whole. Literary critic Elnara Akimova, who calls the novel "a meeting of two different worldviews, two different worlds with all its aspects", interprets Majnun's escape from people and refuge in the forest as a meeting of different worlds: *"The world Majnun lives in is full of cruelty and evil, and his inclination to the forest is a sign that he finds a more civilized, more comfortable way of life there. The author expresses this contradiction by contrasting two environments - the forest with different inhabitants and the world inhabited by people. A symbolic tone is also motivated by a protest against the shrinking role of love in the world. A world that is industrializing day by day, modernizing, subject to the new reality that leaves everything to the hands of robots, accepting the voluntary renunciation of emotions, and on the other side, thinkers who hope to save the world with love."* [1, p.7]. Society has moved so far from its original essence that it considers it wrong not to marry without love, but to be with the one you love.

In the novel "Leyli and Majnun", love is the embodiment of divine purity, because it reflects the point of a person's integration with another person, a person who loves and struggles with society on the path of his love, and a person who is alienated from it and separated from it is a person who achieves his existential freedom. However, in works where love is not presented with such mystical-fantasy, magic-realist shades, it is impossible for it to provide absolute freedom, as love is based on rational thinking and calculations. Tunjal, the hero of Aydın Talibzade's novel "Abuhubb", considers love to be the booty of freedom. It is precisely this tendency to freedom that attracts Fariza: *"Tunjal's unique free behavior and boundless sense of freedom attracted Fariza like a magnet. All the men he saw around him depended on someone, something: they depended on their positions, money, parents, rich relatives, fame, cars, wives, mistresses, children, apartments, villas... Tuncal did not depend on anyone or anything. He could die whenever he wanted, he wouldn't even say "ugh": he didn't feel sorry for himself and said, "Oh God, I'm saying goodbye to life."* [7, p.114-115]. The reason for Tunjal's absolute freedom is his desire to free himself from all relationships and responsibilities. But to what extent can he achieve this?! He considers only love

beyond happiness and unhappiness as "true love". In other words, as a result, Tuncal, who considers feelings that are not bound by any means, does not impose a sense of responsibility on individuals, and does not make lovers dependent on each other, as true love, only at the end, after losing everything, realizes that the existence of true love within the framework of absolute freedom is impossible: "all human against the background of alienation from relationships, including love, is freedom really the freedom that a person needs?" he is helpless in front of the question.

According to existentialist thought, alienation does not arise only on the basis of economic relations, as in Marxism; behavioral stereotypes imposed by society on an individual can distance a person from his true essence. According to J.P.Sartre's theory of alienation, society deprives a person of personal freedom by imposing universal standards of interaction on a person. Society, family, loved ones, which the French thinker summarized under the name of "others", are unable to understand and empathize; they can only hinder individual development and personal freedom.

The core of Hadiyya Shafagat's first novel, which was created as a result of the search for new artistic experiments, which has been engaged in poetry creation for many years, is man's desire for existential freedom and alienation from society. The priority for the novel "Distant People" (2023) suggests a new concept of identity in a development different from the dominant stylistic principles of traditional prose. Techniques such as stream of consciousness and internal monologue revive the projection of the heroes' view of the world from their inner world.

In accordance with the closed model, the novel, distinguished by the special organization of the plot, uses various non-plot elements based on retrospection and multifacetedness, intertextual connection. In the development of "Distant People", stream of consciousness acts as one of the main means of plotting. Thanks to the flow of consciousness combined with the memory technique in the novel, which makes free transitions in time and space through associations, the inner world of the female protagonist opens up, and it becomes possible to go down to her memories, spiritual pains and injuries, starting from her current thoughts. This prominent feature makes it possible for the female protagonist to become alienated from society, and thus not only to herself, but even to her past. In the novel, all of whose characters are nameless, the social reality leaves a deep mark on the character and life of the citizen, forms psychological traumas, the existential situation becomes real, and the fate and essence of the individual is connected with the fate of the nation and the state.

Hadiyya Shafagat's novel "Distant People" brings to the fore the issues of today's uncertainty, the search for purpose and meaning of life, and the relationship between the individual and society against the background of family problems, the contrasts of childhood and adulthood. In the novel, the woman has to choose an alternative against the backdrop of changing structures and historical and political events together with the generations before her, and withdraws

into her own world. Erich Fromm notes that a person who isolates himself is actually not only not happy with it, but even feels anxiety because of it.: "*Isolation breeds anxiety out of anxiety, and ultimately anxiety always comes from it. To be isolated means to be separated from the surrounding world without being able to benefit from human capabilities and power. Therefore, being isolated means not being able to influence the environment, people and generally everything that surrounds us, more precisely, powerlessness; therefore, the surrounding world can reach out to my rights, and I cannot defend myself.*" [13, p.3]. Fear buried in the subconscious is the ruler even in a deserted place. Heroes who are alienated from society and its stereotypes at the first stage, later become alienated from themselves. Because their wishes and desires cannot be concretely defined, their fates do not lead to a conclusion. Although escape from society is seen as a way of salvation, it is as if they do not know what to do in this sheltered world, as if they are not sure that their desire is to get away.

The novel becomes existential with both the male and female protagonist's quest for absolute freedom. "*Existentialism, which gives people the opportunity to choose, resists alienation due to its main typological feature. "Distant people" has both: existential loneliness, the freedom of choice, and the inability to achieve absolute freedom. Of course, freedom is conditional here; because going is a dream and its realization is possible only within the framework of a dream, hallucination.*" [11, p.16] In the novel "Distant People", the path taken by those who want to move away is the distance they travel in thought and imagination, but in reality they count on the spot. Consequently, they live in a sense of alienation not only to society, but to life as a whole, creation, existence, nothingness - everything. Because the life they think is helplessness is like a prison life, the illusion of happiness or peace can make them happy only in imagination. The old man, the old woman, the young man in the novel - everyone goes on the road just to go, not to reach. From this point of view, Hadiyya Shafagat's novel "Distant People" based on the motive of alienation can be read as a parable about the road.

Svetlana Turan's novel "The Wave" (2010, 2019) is another work in which the reason for alienation from society stems from family and childhood traumas. The reason for the estrangement of the nameless hero of this work is not only because he is mentally but also physically traumatized. There are valid reasons for my cold and withdrawn nature. According to the hero of the novel, a person is a being who does not fit into the society and cannot find a place for himself in its general picture. He cannot find any meaning in everyday life, and the concepts and frameworks defined by others seem very meaningless to the young hero. In this respect, the hero of Svetlana Turan's novel "The Wave" can be compared with Meursault in Albert Camus's "The Stranger" (1942). It is true that Meursault comes to these ideas knowing the deep philosophical roots of the idea of the absurd. In the novel "The Stranger", which is considered a manifesto of A. Camus's idea of absolute freedom, Meursault can easily violate the

generally accepted norms of society. The nameless hero of "The Wave" feels good only when he "communicates" with the sea and waves, partially overcomes his loneliness, and the beauty of the sea brings peace to his heart. Meursault's true emotions also show themselves only in relation to nature; loves the sun and the sea, feels comfortable in nature. A sense of the meaninglessness of life reinforces the idea that nothing matters in him, he considers the anxiety of consequences and the framing of one's self to be pointless. Meursault has lost his connections with the surrounding world and spends his days with momentary desires and fleeting dreams. He is not interested in anything spiritual, only satisfying his physical needs. In both novels, the sufferings of the heroes against the background of existential anxiety and, as a result, self-isolation from society are in the foreground.

Although the influence of Albert Camus's attitude to the absurd and "The Stranger" on Svetlana Turan's novel is clear, while Meursault is a character who is unable to love with deep emotions and experiences transient feelings, "The Wave" loves the hero, but does not have the courage to reveal his feelings to his lover. The reason why he can't express his feelings to the other party is that he can't live in the here and now and looks to the future. He always sees the future as shadowy and foggy against the background of the darkness of the past, and because this keeps him constantly worried, he finds comfort in his solitude. He expects a danger behind every step, a blow from the other side, a trap. This is a characteristic, common aspect not only for the novel "The Wave", but for works that bring up the topic of alienation as a whole. He takes so long to make a decision about confessing his feelings to the girl he loves that it's too late: "I was still fast asleep when Imran called me in the morning because I went to sleep late. What Imran told me on the phone woke me up not only from my sleep, but also from my dreams and aspirations. It reminded me that everything is fleeting. He reminded us that nothing is in our hands. I realized with a heavy heart that the decision I made with difficulty a day ago was pointless..." [8, p.206]. The pain of a delayed decision on his love pushes the hero to a radical step: he leaves his mother, on whom he has depended for life. The boy's leaving his mother is interpreted as a symbol of breaking the boundaries and gaining freedom.

Result

In "Man for Himself" (1964), psychoanalyst Erich Fromm sees the cause of everything in man's lack of confidence in his own strength: "*Because we no longer trust our own strength, we lost our faith in people in general, in ourselves, in our abilities to create and build. If we do not believe in our judgments, then we do not have a conscience in the humanistic sense of the word. We are a herd who believe that the path we are on will surely lead us to the goal we desire, because we see others taking the same path. Even though we walk in the dark, we walk boldly because we hear others whistling as we do.*" [13, p.189]. As the desire to

simplify life goes to extremes, over time everything becomes banal, the process of vulgarization is taking place in all social spheres. Thus, everything that was once preached against the personal ideals of the individual - universal values, social goals and objectives, general ideals, etc. becomes completely meaningless and loses its importance. The most diverse forms of pressure and oppression on the individual (economic, political, social, moral, religious, aesthetic, informational) lead to the dehumanization of the person and society, the loss of values and the destruction of ideals. Against the background of all these thoughts, a person lives in isolation from society, but over a long period of time, the passing of a person's life as a life outside of society, away from social consciousness, is rooted in the mood of lack of content. If at first the alienated hero feels himself different from others, lonely in this background, after a certain period of time, he becomes alienated from his solitude - himself and nature, and human life as a whole seems unnecessary.

Acquaintance with the novels of the 2000s shows that the heroes do not always withdraw helplessly after the struggle; From the beginning, there are also those who put up with defeat and raised the flag of surrender without starting the struggle for life and happiness. Their goal is not to win in life, despite all their difficulties and hard faces, but to prove to everyone, to themselves, to life itself, that life is not a place to live.

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